

World Safety Journal

A peer-reviewed journal,
published by the World Safety Organization

Journal Homepage:
<https://worldsafety.org/wso-world-safety-journal/>

Tactical exercises and verification of the effectiveness of crisis planning in the Moravian-Silesian Region. A case study from the Czech Republic

Ivana Kabarová^{1,2*}, Pavel Danihelka^{2,3}, Lenka Schreiberová³, and Kristýna Vavrečková^{2,3}

¹ Regional Authority - Moravian-Silesian Region, Czech Republic

² VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Republic

³ Occupational Safety Research Institute (VUBP), Czech Republic

KEYWORDS

Crisis preparedness
Tactical exercise
Trauma plans
Risk
Extraordinary event

ABSTRACT

Background: Crisis preparation in healthcare facilities should address and resolve both internal and external medical situations. This includes handling the admission of huge numbers of patients during catastrophic disasters, for example. Simultaneously, the management of accidents and disturbances within healthcare facilities, such as fires, power outages, lift functionality, evacuations, and so on, should be managed not only in collaboration with the integrated rescue system, but also in collaboration with higher territorial self-government units, namely regional authorities. The tactical exercises carried out by all components of the rescue system and their preparedness, which frequently show weak places, are one method of testing the efficacy of crisis planning.

Aim: Five tactical exercises were held in the Moravian-Silesian Region from 2015 to 2019 as part of the integrated rescue system's readiness, with the goal of testing the procedures of rescue work in road and rail accidents with a large number of injured people, and then testing the readiness of medical facilities to provide fast, effective, smooth, and well-organized medical care ("launch of the Traumatology Plan").

Datafile and Methods: For the tactical drills, five health care institutions created by the region were chosen. These were volunteer organizations that provided acute inpatient and outpatient care. After reviewing all tactical exercises, it was discovered that communication difficulties, insufficient marking of medical material, the medical team or interveners, and stations were the weak points. Human elements, as well as building and organizational measures in hospitals, proven to be troublesome.

Conclusion: The exercise tested the efficiency and coordination of the integrated rescue system's components, the ability of firefighters to provide first aid to affected people and carry out rescue and recovery work, and revealed the so-called weak points in the trauma plan's activation.

* **Corresponding author:** ivana.kabarova@msk.cz

1. INTRODUCTION

The world's population is constantly encountering, and will probably continue to encounter, extraordinary events that often have a negative impact not only on its activities but also on existence itself, and that includes the consequences of adverse effects on the environment, failure of technology, the economy, and, last but not least, human error. Companies try to prevent the occurrence of extraordinary events or minimize their consequences. The Ministry of the Interior of the Czech Republic has created the Population Protection Concept for 2020 with a view to 2050 (iHETA, 2019). A very important element in the protection of the population is also the level of health care provided by the given country, which is an indicator of its maturity and is determined according to the gross domestic product of the country.

Inpatient medical facilities prepare for emergencies and crisis situations as part of risk management and by creating plans such as trauma plans, pandemic plans, or evacuation plans. In the Czech Republic, after 1989, extensive trauma centers and emergency services were established, which are prepared for the occurrence of extraordinary events. Their task is to eliminate the medical consequences of a mass disaster in cooperation with the components of the integrated rescue system. Mastering the treatment of these serious conditions is ensured mainly by means of prepared trauma plans. These plans are developed for the mass admission of people with various types of disabilities, such as trauma, contamination (biological or chemical), substance intoxication, burns, and radiation effects. Traumatological plans define the tasks and methods of management in the healthcare sector with a focus on activities in the event of mass accidents, describe the activities of the operational centers of the medical rescue service, and provide contacts for healthcare services and facilities (hospitals). It also contains the impacts of selected extraordinary events on the health of the population, including the forces and means for ensuring health care (OSRI, 2019).

2. LEGAL REQUIREMENTS IN THE CZECH REPUBLIC

The obligation to prepare a trauma plan follows the current legislation of the Czech Republic. Inpatient medical facilities and facilities that provide one-day care are required to prepare a trauma plan, in which they adjust the set of measures that are applied in the event of a mass disaster, and to update it at least once every two years. The facility submits one copy of the plan to the relevant administrative authority (regional office, department of health) within 30 days from the date of its processing or updating. Processing is based on local conditions and possibilities and the results of discussing them (Act on Health Services 2011, 47, p. 4758).

2.1 The Trauma Plan

The content of the trauma plan is precisely defined by the applicable legislation and entails three parts: basic, operative, and auxiliary. The basic part defines, in addition to basic data about the organization (hospital), an overview and evaluation of possible internal and external sources of risks and threats to the medical facility and the definition of the provider's scope of activity. The operative part defines the procedures for the implementation of measures for the reception of a mass accident, cooperation with the medical rescue service, and individual workplaces in an inpatient medical facility. Part of the content is also an overview of connections and how to ensure the protection of workers' health. The auxiliary part contains overviews of, for example, concluded contracts with supplier institutions, a list of medical devices, medicines, and medical personnel, labeling principles, records, and other related documents.

However, it is possible to state succinctly that the trauma plans developed by inpatient medical facilities define potential external and internal risks that are present in or close to their organization and may pose a threat to the occurrence of extraordinary events or accidents. They define the contact points for communication with the integrated rescue system, including the characteristics of possible types of injuries and their treatment in the mentioned facility and the possible number of patient admissions in the time horizon. In the final part of the plans, personnel provision, material and technical equipment in the event of an emergency, and the contractual provision of companies in the event of a power outage are specified. Competences are also listed, whether from management to mini-trauma teams in operating and procedure rooms.

Prepared, regularly updated, and reviewed (e.g., tactical exercises) trauma plans must respect and fulfill the currently valid state legislation; however, some risks may still be underestimated. In most cases, existing emergency plans focus on mechanical risks, but it is also worth considering chemical, biological, and radiation risks, which can overload inpatient medical facilities. Threats with biological weapons began to appear in the world (e.g., the war conflict in Ukraine), and with them came preparations for a large intake of wounded contaminated with dangerous substances. An important project was, for example, TOXI-triage, which was based on the concept of dual use, namely multipurpose applications for our technologies within general emergency medicine (toxicity) and the environment. The Horizon 2020 project was also focused on the community and its rescue (Toxi-Triage, <http://www.toxi-triage.eu/>). The Fire and Rescue Service of the Moravian-Silesian Region took part in this international project.

2.2 Definition of an inpatient medical facility and its function for crisis planning

Medical facility means premises intended for the provision of medical services. Health services can be divided according to the form of health care provided in health facilities into ambulatory, one-day, inpatient, and health care provided in the patient's own social environment (e.g., visiting service, home care, artificial pulmonary ventilation, which can be provided as part of the provision of home care), and subsequently the type of care. Bedside care is understood as (Act on Health Services 2011, 9, p. 4734):

health care that cannot be provided on an outpatient basis and requires the hospitalization of the patient for its provision.

This care must be provided as part of continuous operation. Accurate personnel security, including material and technical equipment for all fields and forms of health care provided, is clearly anchored by the legislation of the Czech Republic. Without compliance with applicable legislation and conditions, inpatient care in healthcare facilities, outpatient care, or home care cannot be provided.

2.3 Risk Management

Risk management in the healthcare sector focuses on preventing the occurrence of potential unwanted and negative consequences of a situation or event (Terje et al., 2018), which may threaten the functionality of an inpatient medical facility to the extent that the crisis situation deepens.

A crisis is a situation (OSRI, 2019, p. 48):

in which the balance between the basic characteristics of the system (the mission, philosophy, values, goals, and style of functioning of the system) on the one hand and the attitude of the surrounding environment towards the system on the other hand is significantly disturbed.

Currently, within the Czech Republic, medical facilities are constantly preparing to deal with extraordinary events and crisis situations through risk management activities and the creation of, for example, trauma plans, pandemic plans, or evacuation plans. The two basic concepts of all risk management include "danger" and "risk", when:

- Danger is understood as a source of potential harm.
- Risk is the effect of uncertainty on the achievement of goals.
 - The effect is understood as a deviation from the expected (requested), and in general, it can be not only negative but also positive.
 - The goals can then have different aspects (such as financial, health, and safety goals) and be applied at different levels (such as the strategic level or the level concerning the entire healthcare facility and its processes) (Standard Czech, 2010).

The risk management process according to ISO 31,000 is subsequently composed of two parts, namely, "risk assessment" and "risk treatment" (Daníhelka et al., 2014). An extraordinary event is defined as:

harmful effects of forces and phenomena caused by human activity and natural influences, as well as accidents that threaten life, health, property, or the environment and require rescue and liquidation work. (The Law on the Integrated Rescue System 2000, 7, p. 3464)

Extraordinary events, both external risks (which trigger a trauma plan or other action requiring a change in the functioning of the device) and internal risks (leading to device function failure, e.g., fire, power interruption), threaten inpatient medical facilities.

2.4 Population's Perception of Risk

Perceptions of risk and actual risks reveal a mismatch between the scenarios we fear and the ones that are really seriously harmful to us. The perception of risk and real danger are described in the work of Susanna Hertrichová (Bernstein, 2018). According to the illustration, the greatest danger for the population is a terrorist attack or air disaster (Fig. 1). At the same time, the real bigger threats are oncological diseases (Institute of Health Information and Statistics of the Czech Republic, <https://www.uzis.cz/index-en.php>), traffic accidents, the effects of environmental pollution, and even the impact of an asteroid.

Figure 1. Perception of Risk and Actual Danger (Bernstein, Alison. *Risk in Perspective*, 2018)

3. VERIFICATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CRISIS PLANNING IN THE MORAVIAN-SILESIA REGION

The integrated rescue system in the Czech Republic consists of the basic components, namely the Fire and Rescue Service, volunteer firefighting units, the medical rescue service, and the police. These emergency services are constantly preparing for emergency management, reviewing trauma plans from medical facilities, and conducting tactical exercises. The Health Department of the Moravian-Silesian Regional Authority is involved in the preparation and implementation of these large-scale tactical exercises.

3.1 Participants

The region chose five health facilities to participate in the tactical exercises as contributory organizations. The activity of all participating hospitals within the framework of tactical exercises is the provision and organization of inpatient and outpatient care, namely basic and specialized diagnostic, curative, and preventive care. The total capacity of beds in each hospital was around 450.

3.2 Procedure

As part of the readiness of the integrated rescue system, five tactical exercises took place in the Moravian-Silesian Region in the period 2015–2019, the aim of which was to check the procedures of rescue work in road and railway accidents with many injured people and subsequently the readiness of medical facilities to provide fast, efficient, smooth, and well-organized health care ("launching the Traumatology Plan"). The exercise tested the ability to act and the coordination of the components of the integrated rescue system, as well as the ability of firefighters to provide first aid to injured people and to carry out rescue and rescue work (Figs. 2–4). The aim of the exercise was to practice the method of sorting the injured. Among the important results of the exercise was the discovery of a number of

possibilities for improvement in the organization of one's intervention and weaknesses, both technical and organizational. At the same time, shortcomings in the field of communication were also revealed.

3.3 Analysis and Results

Evaluation of tactical training and identified shortcomings

In all instances of tactical exercises, poor communication to medical facilities was the obvious cause of the trauma plan's problematic launch and delay. The Regional Operations and Information Center received information about the injured only after the first patients arrived at the medical facility, or the contact point was not informed at all about the launch of the trauma plan. Misinformation also occurred when the number of injured people brought in differed from the reported number and the actual admission to the medical facility, and in one case, the hospital was not informed about the termination of the trauma plan. The interveners who worked at the scene of the accident brought three injured people by themselves in private cars without being informed of the integrated rescue system or moving outside their designated areas in the medical facility, sometimes even complicating the work of the medical personnel. Their cooperation, as well as the cooperation of psychologists in the health sector and security workers who waited a long time for instructions or did not report to the Regional Operations and Information Center, was negatively evaluated. In the case of the first exercise, the telephone connection was overloaded. For other exercises, the medical staff did not report after activation, did not proceed according to the notification decree, but still managed to summon the medical staff after activating the trauma plan within 15 minutes.

Another problematic point was the designation not only of the medical team, including interventions, but also of the material used, which was part and parcel of the integrated rescue system during the initial intervention and was also handed over to the patients during their pre-hospital intervention. This situation resulted in the difficulty of determining the correct records of the used medical material. Among the problems were the lack of reflective vests and, in the first case of tactical training, the medical documentation and administration of the participants in the traffic accident. The masking of the mannequins and their injuries was very authentic, and during the transport there was an inappropriate marking that was insufficiently attached; there was a risk of it being lost during the transport, or the marking was illegible and therefore practically unusable.

The third problematic risk during the activation of the trauma plan included the construction-technical and organizational measures of medical facilities that created problematic areas, the failure to ensure smooth operation of the elevator with the injured, obstacles when handling the injured (e.g., flower pots, inappropriately placed benches, etc.), and very small spaces, for example, for relatives of the disabled.

The medical rescue service evaluated the insufficient marking of positions for the disabled as the most problematic part of the tactical exercise, and the leaders of the intervening functions (e.g., the intervention commander) were insufficiently marked. In two cases, the points of entry to the pre-hospital care station were also insufficiently marked. There was also an inappropriate placement of deceased patients who were close to affected and conscious patients. The shortage was also noted during the intervention in materials such as thermofoil or sorting tapes. In adverse climatic conditions, there is a need to ensure sufficient thermal comfort for patients waiting for triage.

The failure of human factors occurred in the last case, when the dispatcher of the medical operation

center of the medical emergency service did not realize the necessity of activating the traumatological plan of the medical facility and constantly verified the diagnoses that would be admitted to the medical facility as part of a tactical exercise. The dispatcher continuously verified the messages and notified the medical facility in advance of the upcoming exercise.

During the tactical exercises, the Fire Rescue Corps negatively assessed the confusing situation of marking which members of the integrated rescue system perform patient triage and its termination, as well as the interchangeability of the colors yellow and green in the first case of the exercise, resulting in non-marking and missing records of medical materials. There was also insufficient marking of the manhole covers, and the marking of the manhole location was made only by a sign on the tunnel wall at a height of about 3 meters. This marking is invisible to firefighters traveling near the ground when the tunnel is smoking.

For the Czech Republic Police, in two cases there were communication breakdowns between the commander of the intervention, the command of the units, cooperation with medical facilities, and their contact persons for providing data for the identification of people in a traffic accident.

Figure 2. Tactical Exercise: Mass Traffic Accident, 2017. (Fire Rescue Service of The Moravian-Silesian Region, 2017)

Figure 3. Tactical Exercise: Collision Between A Bus and An Excavator (Kabarová, Ivana, 2018)

Figure 4. Tactical Exercise: Members of The Integrated Rescue System Triage Patients (Kabarová, I., 2018)

Figure 5. Tactical Exercise: Train Accident in The Tunnel (Fire Rescue Service of The Moravian-Silesian Region, 2019)

At the same time, the Department of Health, Regional Office of the Moravian-Silesian Region, developed a graphic list of the capacities of providers of acute medical inpatient care based on the experience of tactical exercises and trauma plans of individual health service providers. The list consists of the data of health care facilities in the region that provide both inpatient and one-day care, with an indication of all contact points in individual facilities. The acute inpatient care provider is obliged to set up a contact point in order to ensure the patient's admission and the immediate continuation of the provision of health services. At the same time, there is an obligation to ensure continuous transmission of information on the number of available emergency beds to the contact point, information on restrictions on the provision of urgent care, and cooperation in rescue and liquidation work when dealing with extraordinary events and crisis situations when requested by the provider of emergency medical services (Law on Emergency Medical Services 2011, 6, p. 4841). Furthermore, the data in the table informs about the readiness to treat the injured (e.g., burns, trauma) and the number of immediately allocated beds in the event of an emergency in the Moravian-Silesian Region, with the expansion of the capacity of the bed pool within 2 hours and 24 hours. The data is regularly updated and accessible to members of the crisis teams.

4. CONCLUSION

The exercise tested the efficiency and coordination of the components of the integrated rescue system and the ability of firefighters to provide first aid to affected people and to carry out rescue and recovery work. It revealed the so-called weak points in the activation of the trauma plan. The Department of Health, Regional Office of the Moravian-Silesian Region, within the framework of current and still urgent challenges, constantly supports the electronic sharing of data and communication in the health sector and, at the same time, constantly develops projects to improve the quality and safety of the population for the health care provided in the region in cooperation with the integrated rescue system. The support includes financial subsidies for the integrated rescue system, especially for the ambulance service in the Moravian-Silesian Region. The support focuses on further training of health professionals, purchases of ambulances, support for IT systems, and telemedicine, including

modernization and strengthening of the resilience of the backbone network of health care providers with regard to potential threats (focusing on acute care—disciplines that are linked to emergency admissions—in order to increase the resilience of the health system). Furthermore, the construction of other urgent incomes, the construction of exit bases and posts, and other important projects in the field of acute and follow-up care

Since November 2018, with the support of the regional authority, the Department of Health, another project, the First Responder System, has been put into operation in the Moravian-Silesian Region, i.e., a system that cooperates between the Moravian-Silesian Medical Rescue Service and volunteer rescuers. First responder is a globally recognized concept of informing and activating trained rescuers in the event of indications of a direct threat to the patient's life. In some cases, registered and trained volunteers can be informed by the operation center about the occurrence of a patient in a life-threatening condition in their vicinity, and the patient can be provided with basic first aid even before the arrival of the medical emergency crew. In conclusion, we also point out that inpatient medical facilities should prepare and rehearse their readiness for all real emergencies that may occur, such as criminal attacks (for example, terrorist attacks, attacks by mentally ill persons, cyber-attacks), interruption of the supply of commodities (energy crisis), migration waves, etc.

5. LIMITATIONS

Another tactical exercise in the Moravian-Silesian region was prepared for the year 2020 to check the trauma plan at the Ostrava University Hospital with the use of highly specialized centers (e.g., the Burn Center). The hospital's bed capacity was around 1,300. Due to other events that hit the Moravian-Silesian region in the period 2020–2022, including COVID-19, the migration wave of refugees from Ukraine, and an emergency that hit the University Hospital in Ostrava at the end of 2019 (the attack of an active shooter), a tactical exercise was held in April 2023. In the same month, another tactical exercise took place with the Integrated Rescue System in a smaller hospital in the Moravian-Silesian Region, the hospital in Blavec.

DEDICATION

This research was financially supported by institutional support for the long-term conceptual development of the research organization for the years 2018–2022, and is part of research task 01-S4-2022, OSH in a Transforming Society, dealt with by the Occupational Safety Research Institute in the period 2022–2024.

REFERENCES

- Act on Health Services. Low No. 372/2011 Coll. <https://www.zakonyprolidi.cz/cs/2011-372>
- Bernstein, A. (2018). *Risk in Perspective*. <https://scimoms.com/risk-perspective-series-intro/>
- Danihelka, P. (2014). *Analýza a management rizik závažných havárií s nebezpečnými látkami v energetice* (1st ed). University of Mining - Technical University Ostrava.
- iHETA. (2019). The structure of costs in the Czech healthcare system and their allocation mechanisms. *Institute for Politics and Society: Institute for health economics a technology assessment*. <https://www.politikaspolecnost.cz/analyzy/struktura-nakladu-v-ceskem-zdravotnictvi-a-mechanismy-jejich-alokace/>
- OSRI. (2019). Occupational Safety Research Institute. *Interpretive glossary of some terms used in risk analysis and assessment for the purposes of the Major Accident Prevention Act*. <https://vubp.cz/prevence-zavaznych-havarii/metodiky/>
- Standards Czech. (2010). *Risk management - Glossary* (Guideline 73) (TNI 01 0350 - 010350)
- Law on Emergency Medical Services. Low No. 374/2011 Coll.
- Law on the Integrated Rescue System. Low No. 239/2000 Coll.

Terje, A., Yakov, B., Henning, B., Tony, C., Enrique, L., Michael, G., Seth, G., Wolfgang, K., Ortwin, R., Kimberly, M. T., Enrico, Z. (2018). Society for Risk Analysis Glossary. <https://www.sra.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SRA-Glossary-FINAL.pdf>

AUTHORS

Ivana Kabarová is a Ph.D. candidate in the department of Safety Engineering at VSB—the Technical University of Ostrava—researching the management of non-therapeutic risks of inpatient medical facilities in emergency situations. Ivana worked as a nurse at the University Hospital in Ostrava in the intensive care unit of the trauma centre for 17 years. She was also involved in improving quality and safety in the healthcare sector as an internal auditor. Nowadays, she works at the health department of the Regional Authority, Moravian-Silesian Region, cooperating with the components of the integrated rescue system in the preparation of tactical exercises in the region.

Professor Pavel Danihelka, graduated from the Faculty of Natural Sciences of Charles University in Prague, majoring in chemistry, gradually devoted himself to the environment and risks of natural and technological origin. He focuses on research and risk management and environmental security, is involved in UN activities (UNDRR, UNDP, UNECE) related to disaster risk reduction, and is a member of NATO's Independent Scientific Expert Group in the Science for Peace and Security program. He served as the Czech Republic's national delegate on the Horizon 2020 Secure Societies program committee. Furthermore, he works at the University of Mining and Technology in Ostrava and the Occupational Safety Research Institute, Czech Republic.

Dr. Lenka Schreiberová graduated from the Faculty of Mining and Geology of the Technical University of Ostrava, with a specialization in Environmental Protection in Industry. She focuses on research and risk management, environmental security, and the protection and safety of workers. She has experience with politics at the local level as a Member of the Municipal District 7 Assembly, and now she works as a researcher at the Occupational Safety Research Institute in Ostrava, Czech Republic.

Kristýna Vavrečková, graduated from the Medical Faculty of the University of Ostrava with a specialization in public health. Kristýna holds the title of Safety Engineer from the Faculty of Safety Engineering at the Technical University of Ostrava, where she is currently a Ph.D. candidate, focusing on safety culture. As a Health, Safety, and Environment Advisor, she has practical experience in the epidemiological prevention of COVID-19. Kristýna is currently working as a visiting research associate at Curtin University in Western Australia and also as a researcher at the Occupational Safety Research Institute, Czech Republic.

